

NANODIAMOND-TREATED FLAX: IMPROVING PROPERTIES OF NATURAL FIBERS

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NANODIAMOND

FLAX

IMPROVED PROPERTIES

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Talk outline

Motivation

Results

Modeling

Outlook

Q&A

- Natural fibers
- Nanodiamonds

- Nanodiamond treatment
- Mechanical properties
- Comparison between flax and cotton

- Explanation of experimental findings

- New application

Why natural fibers?

Fig. 1: Fiber reinforced composite material [1]

Advantages:

- More sustainable (biodegradable, less energy consumption, less costs) [2]
- Competitive specific mechanical properties (strength to density ratio) [2]
- Excellent damping properties

Disadvantages:

- Lower ultimate strength than synthetic fibers
- Variability in properties
- Hydrophilic (poor compatibility with matrix)

Where are natural fibers used?

Cost and weight saving:

Fig. 2: Components of Mercedes E-Class from late 1990s using natural fiber composites [1]

Utilizing special properties:

Fig. 3: Guitar made from flax fiber for acoustic reasons [2]

Reducing the gap to glass fibers

Bast fibres: ● Flax ● Hemp ● Jute
Leaf fibres: ● Pineapple ● Sisal ● Banana

Seed fibres: ● Cotton ● Oil palm ● Coir
Other fibres: ● Bamboo ● Wood pulp

Fig. 4: Comparison of typical strength and stiffness performance of various plant fibers [1]

How can nanodiamonds help?

Fig. 5: ND of 3-5nm size [1]

Treatments:

- Chemicals change the composition of fibers
- Nano-particles (CNT, graphene) bond to and cover fibers

Nanodiamonds (NDs):

- Exceptional mechanical resistance (hardness, tensile strength...)
- **Tunable surface properties:**
 - Surface groups (compatible to organic natural fibers)
 - Hydrophobic ↔ Hydrophilic
 - Zeta potential
- Bio-compatible, **non-toxic** (unlike CNT, graphene ...) [2]

Nanodiamond treatment

Fig. 6: Picture of dry flax fabric on base plate (a) and wet flax fabric mounted for treatment (b) [1]

Materials:

- Standard off the shelf flax fabric for composites
- 150g/m² 2/2 twill woven flax fabric (Libeco NV, Belgium)
- Hydrogen-terminated nanodiamonds (Carbodeon Ltd Oy, Finland)

Cleaning of flax:

- Sonication in isopropanol (3 min) and deionized water (20 min)

ND treatment:

- ND dispersion of 0.3%
- Sonication for 30 min
- Drying on hot plate at 60 °C [2]

Nanodiamond density

Fig. 7: White light image of untreated (a) and nanodiamond treated flax (b) [1]

Fig. 8: SEM image of flax yarn [1]

Density estimation:

- Weight based → ~35 mg ND on 260 mm × 450 mm fabric

All elementary fibers are fully covered with NDs

Mechanical properties

Tensile strength of single threads:

- Based on ISO13934-1:2013
- Increase in UTS by ~ **24 %** with decrease in strain by ~ **11 %**

Almost all tested ND-treated flax threads are stronger than untreated flax threads at the same elongation

Fig. 9: Ultimate tensile strength (UTS) as a function of elongation [1]

Yarn structure and clamping

Fig. 10: SEM image of flax yarn [1]

Fig. 11: Overlapping effects influencing the correlation between yarn strength and twist angle [2]

Fig. 12: Different clamping conditions [3]

NDs increase cohesion between elementary fibers, which makes the yarn stronger

Cotton experiments by S. Houshyar et al.

Fig. 13: (a) Flax plant drawing [1]; (b) Cotton boll image [2];
 (c) SEM image of single flax fibers [3];
 (d) SEM image of cotton fibers [4]

Tensile strength improvement with nanodiamond treatment:

Flax:	Cotton:
+ 24% [1]	+ 40% [2]

Fig. 14: Schematic of the nanodiamond interacting with cotton [5]

Proposed explanation for tensile strength increase

Fig. 15: Schematic (not to scale) of a thread's cross-section; Nanodiamonds bond between elementary fibers, increasing the adhesion between the elementary fibers and strengthening the thread; Additional water is confined by the hydrophobic nanodiamonds to further increase the adhesion between the elementary fibers [1]

Nanodiamond induced force

Fig. 16: Superposition of electrolytic force and dispersion force as a function of fiber-nanodiamond-distance [1]

Zeta potential difference:

Flax:

– 5 mV in 1mMol
KCl (pH 7) [3]

Cotton:

– 15 mV in 1mMol
KCl (pH 7) [4]

Tensile strength improvement with nanodiamond treatment:

Flax:

+ 24% [1]

Cotton:

+ 40% [2]

+ 67%

Chemical composition; Cellulose ratio [5]:

Flax:

70%

Cotton:

90%

Conclusion

Non-toxic nanodiamond treatment of flax:

- Increased UTS by + 24%

⇒ Decreases performance gap to glass fibers

Modeling of interaction between ND and natural fibers:

- Introduction of electrolytic and dispersion forces
- Stronger interaction with cotton than with flax

⇒ Higher strength improvements for ND-treated cotton

⇒ Presumably because of cotton's lower zeta potentials

Future work

Improving properties of natural fibers:

- Testing the zeta potential hypophysis by tuning the zeta potential of flax
- Combining ND-treatment with chemical treatments

⇒ Increase strength of natural fibers

Testing ND-treated flax in composite applications:

- Performing standard composite performance tests (tensile test, compression, bending ...)
- Testing interface (pull-out tests)

⇒ Finding beneficial applications for natural fibers

Impact fatigue test for wind turbine blade erosion:

Fig. 17: Impact number to reach first matrix material loss ($v = 160\text{m/s}$)

Fig. 18: Mass loss as a function of accumulated impact energy for impact velocities of 160m/s

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Q & A

Would you like to collaborate on a related topic?

Please contact me in the coffee break or by e-mail:
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